

Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics

Optical, electrical and surface properties of bare and Al-doped nanocrystalline ZnO thin films prepared by pulsed laser deposition on interdigital electrodes --Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:							
Full Title:	Optical, electrical and surface properties of bare and Al-doped nanocrystalline ZnO thin films prepared by pulsed laser deposition on interdigital electrodes						
Article Type:	Original Research						
Keywords:	ZnO thin films; photocurrent; pulsed laser deposition; interdigitated electrodes						
Corresponding Author:	Neda Neykova Czech technical University in Prague: Ceske Vysoke Uceni Technicke v Praze Prague, CZECHIA						
Corresponding Author Secondary Information:							
Corresponding Author's Institution:	Czech technical University in Prague: Ceske Vysoke Uceni Technicke v Praze						
Corresponding Author's Secondary Institution:							
First Author:	Zdeněk Remeš						
First Author Secondary Information:							
Order of Authors:	Zdeněk Remeš Neda Neykova Naini Jain Rupendra Kumar Sharma Jakub Holovský Egor Ukraintsev Jaroslav Kuliček Bohuslav Rezek Hua Shu Hsu						
Order of Authors Secondary Information:							
Funding Information:	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Grantová Agentura České Republiky (24-10607J)</td> <td>Dr. Zdeněk Remeš</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Ministerstvo Školství, Mládeže a Tělovýchovy (CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617)</td> <td>Dr. Jakub Holovský</td> </tr> <tr> <td>National Science and Technology Council (NSTC 113-2923-M-153 -001 -MY3)</td> <td>Prof. Hua Shu Hsu</td> </tr> </table>	Grantová Agentura České Republiky (24-10607J)	Dr. Zdeněk Remeš	Ministerstvo Školství, Mládeže a Tělovýchovy (CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617)	Dr. Jakub Holovský	National Science and Technology Council (NSTC 113-2923-M-153 -001 -MY3)	Prof. Hua Shu Hsu
Grantová Agentura České Republiky (24-10607J)	Dr. Zdeněk Remeš						
Ministerstvo Školství, Mládeže a Tělovýchovy (CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617)	Dr. Jakub Holovský						
National Science and Technology Council (NSTC 113-2923-M-153 -001 -MY3)	Prof. Hua Shu Hsu						
Abstract:	Zinc oxide (ZnO) is a low-cost, environmentally friendly material with unique optical properties and a wide variety of nano- and microstructures, making it attractive for applications in energy conversion, scintillators, photocatalytic wastewater treatment, electrochemical energy storage, and sensing. In this work, nominally undoped and Al-doped nanocrystalline ZnO thin films were deposited by pulsed laser deposition (PLD) on commercial gold-based interdigitated electrodes (IDEs). Surface morphology and structure were characterized using Correlative Probe and Electron Microscopy (CPEM), combining Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) to perform spatially correlated measurements. PLD resulted in the formation of larger crystals in thicker ZnO layers, while Al doping only slightly affected grain size. Optical and optoelectronic properties were investigated by photothermal deflection (PDS) and photocurrent spectroscopy (PCS). The mobility edge was found to lie approximately 0.3 eV below the band gap. Space-charge-limited currents were						

	observed at low voltages. Persistent photoconductivity indicates potential issues with charge transport.
Additional Information:	
Question	Response
<p>Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics considers only outstanding papers that make a distinct contribution to the field of experimental electronic materials. This includes optoelectronic and photonic materials as well.</p> <p>Please explain in point form why your work is outstanding and what distinguishes this work from past work. What are the outstanding and exceptional contributions of this paper? How does it contribute to the state-of-the art?</p>	<p>This study integrates pulsed laser deposition-grown bare and Al-doped ZnO films with commercial IDEs for low-cost device prototyping. Using correlative AFM-in-SEM (CPEM), it links morphology with electronic properties. A mobility edge $\sim 0.3\text{eV}$ below the band gap is identified, revealing trap-related transport. Space-charge-limited conduction and persistent photoconductivity are observed. The work offers a comprehensive structure-property analysis, advancing ZnO-based optoelectronic applications.</p>
Is this manuscript part of an ongoing Special Issue (SI), and were you asked to submit to this Special Issue?	No
Were you asked by one of our editors to resubmit your manuscript because of textual overlap or not complying with scientific guidelines?	No
<p>Does your manuscript comply with the journal's standards and instructions to authors on notation, significant figures, experimental errors and the use of the Scherrer equation? Instructions to authors can be accessed at "https://www.springer.com/journal/10854/submit-guidelines#linksAndDownloads". Manuscripts that do not comply with instructions to authors will be rejected.</p>	Yes
<p>How many of your own papers have you self-cited in this manuscript? (Your paper may be rejected if the Editor feels self-citations are excessive or not related to the work in the paper)</p>	3

Optical, electrical and surface properties of bare and Al-doped nanocrystalline ZnO thin films prepared by pulsed laser deposition on interdigital electrodes

Zdeněk Remes^{1*}, Neda Neykova^{1,2*}, Naini Jain², Rupendra Kumar Sharma², Jakub Holovský^{1,2}, Egor Ukraintsev², Jaroslav Kuliček², Bohuslav Rezek², and Hua Shu Hsu³

¹*Institute of Physics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Cukrovarnická 10, 162 00, Prague, Czech Republic*

²*Faculty for Electrical Engineering, Czech Technical University in Prague, Technická 2, 166 27 Prague, Czech Republic*

³*National Pingtung University, Department of Applied Physics, Taiwan*

*Corresponding authors: Z. Remes, N. Neykova (e-mail: remes@fzu.cz, neda.neykova@fel.cvut.cz)

Keywords: ZnO thin films, photocurrent, pulsed laser deposition, interdigitated electrodes

Abstract

Zinc oxide (ZnO) is a low-cost, environmentally friendly material with unique optical properties and a wide variety of nano- and microstructures, making it attractive for applications in energy conversion, scintillators, photocatalytic wastewater treatment, electrochemical energy storage, and sensing. In this work, nominally undoped and Al-doped nanocrystalline ZnO thin films were deposited by pulsed laser deposition (PLD) on commercial gold-based interdigitated electrodes (IDEs). Surface morphology and structure were characterized using Correlative Probe and Electron Microscopy (CPEM), combining Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) to perform spatially correlated measurements. PLD resulted in the formation of larger crystals in thicker ZnO layers, while Al doping only slightly affected grain size. Optical and optoelectronic properties were investigated by photothermal deflection (PDS) and photocurrent spectroscopy (PCS). The mobility edge was found to lie approximately 0.3 eV below the band gap. Space-charge-limited currents were observed at low voltages. Persistent photoconductivity indicates potential issues with charge transport.

Introduction

Zinc oxide (ZnO) is a well-established semiconductor material recognized for its low cost, non-toxicity, wide band gap (~3.37 eV) and high exciton binding energy (~60 meV). These properties make ZnO an attractive material for a broad range of applications including optoelectronics, sensors, transparent conductors, and photocatalysis [1–3]. The material's versatility is further enhanced by its tunability through doping and nano structuring, which allow for controlled manipulation of electrical conductivity and optical absorption [4]. A broad range of dopants—such as F, B, Al, Ga, In, and Sn—has been explored to achieve conductive ZnO films [5]. Among these, Al stands out as a cost-effective, abundant, and non-toxic option. Its small ionic radius enables effective substitution without significantly disrupting the ZnO lattice structure, thereby enhancing carrier concentration [6]. Consequently, Al-doped ZnO films have emerged as promising, low-cost alternatives to indium tin oxide in photovoltaic and transparent conductive applications [7,8]. ZnO thin films are also employed in acetone sensors used for environmental monitoring, industrial air quality control, and medical diagnostics [9–11].

Pulsed laser deposition (PLD) has gained recognition in recent years as a precise method for fabricating nanocrystalline ZnO thin films. The technique allows fine control over film thickness, composition, and stoichiometry—parameters critical for incorporating ZnO into microelectronic devices. When ZnO is deposited on patterned structures such as interdigital electrodes (IDEs), it shows potential for microscale sensing platforms requiring high surface sensitivity and reproducibility[12].

Our earlier work focused on nanocrystalline ZnO films (<100 nm thick) deposited on fused silica by PLD, examining how Al doping influences optical absorbance and photoluminescence (PL) properties [13]. At low temperatures (~4 K), excitonic and defect-related emission bands were observed at ~365 nm and ~650 nm, with a surface-related blue PL band appearing in some samples [14,15]. This blue emission disappeared after annealing at 500 °C in air [16]. Hall effect measurements confirmed n-type conductivity, albeit with relatively low mobility, indicative of defect-related scattering. Additionally, persistent photoconductivity under UV illumination pointed to deep trap states influencing carrier transport—highlighting potential applications in UV detectors and transparent conductive oxides.

Simultaneously, advancements in microscopy have enabled more comprehensive analysis of nanostructured materials. Correlative Probe and Electron Microscopy (CPEM)—which integrates AFM and SEM—permits concurrent topographic and electronic characterization of identical regions, making it invaluable for studies of heterogeneous thin films where surface features significantly impact functionality.

In this study, we investigate nominally undoped and Al-doped ZnO thin films deposited via PLD on commercial gold-based IDEs. We employ PDS and PCS for optical and photoelectrical characterization and use AFM and CPEM to correlate morphology with electrical behavior. This integrated approach provides new insights into the interplay between structure and performance in doped ZnO films, supporting their development for next generation sensing and electronic devices.

Table 1 Summary of nanocrystalline ZnO films deposited by PLD on commercial IDEs (10 μm electrode spacing), detailing target composition, number of laser pulses, film thickness (d), refractive index (n), absorption coefficient at 1 eV (α), and electrical resistivity (ρ).

Sample	target	pulses	d (nm)	n	ρ (Ω)
A	ZnO	20 000	85	1.92	2×10^6
B	ZnO & 1 wt % Al	40 000	77	1.80	50
C	ZnO	100 000	300	1.92	6×10^6

Experiment

Polycrystalline ZnO and 1 wt.% Al-doped ZnO layers were deposited on commercially available gold-based Interdigitated Electrodes IDE1-Au – 10/10 μm (90 pairs of electrodes, electrode width 10 μm, electrode distance 10 μm) on a glass substrate (MicruX Fluidic, S.L., Gijón, Asturias) by pulsed laser deposition (PLD) setup from TSST B.V. equipped with KrF ($\lambda = 248$ nm) excimer laser COMPex 50. For the deposition, stoichiometric ZnO and 1 wt.% Al-doped ZnO targets were ablated using a laser pulse energy of approximately 24 mJ (measured inside the chamber), corresponding to a fluence of 1.2 J/cm², respectively. The substrates were mounted on a rotating holder (5 rpm) and maintained at room temperature (25 °C) during deposition. The base pressure before the deposition was 10⁻⁴ Pa. The excimer laser beam was

1 focused onto a spot area of 2 mm^2 and operated at a repetition rate of 20 Hz. The number of
2 pulses varied between 20,000 and 100,000 to achieve different film thicknesses. During
3 deposition, oxygen was introduced at a process pressure of 10 Pa and a flow rate of $10 \text{ cm}^3/\text{min}$.
4 Three polycrystalline ZnO layers were deposited, and their thickness, optical, and electrical
5 properties are summarized in Table 1.
6

7 The samples were studied by LiteScope AFM (NenoVision Ltd., Brno, Czechia) placed inside
8 EVO 10 SEM (Carl Zeiss AG, Oberkochen, Germany) using nose type self-sensing Akiyama
9 cantilever (NenoVision) to perform Correlative Probe and Electron Microscopy (CPEM), that
10 integrates Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) to
11 perform simultaneous correlated measurements of the same sample region for 3D visualization.
12 SEM images were obtained with 10 kV voltage, 10 pA current and 9.6 mm working distance.
13 CPEM image was created using MATLAB script for aligning and cropping and Gwyddion
14 software[17,18], designed for the visualization and analysis of data from scanning probe
15 microscopy techniques [19,20].
16
17
18

19 The surface properties were also studied by (AFM) using Dimension ICON AFM (Bruker
20 Corporation, Billerica, MA, USA) with untreated Budget Sensors Multi75Al cantilever
21 (Inovative Solutions Bulgaria Ltd., Sofia, Bulgaria) in Peak Force Quantitative
22 Nanomechanical Mapping (PFQNM) mode. In PFQNM mode, the AFM probe taps the surface
23 at a fixed frequency (much lower than conventional tapping mode) and measures the force–
24 distance curve at every pixel. Unlike tapping mode, where resonance dynamics dominate,
25 PFQNM directly controls the peak force applied during each tap. Two $1 \times 1 \text{ }\mu\text{m}^2$ spots were
26 studied on each sample, one spot on the gold part and one spot on the glass part of the MicruX
27 substrate. Two $50 \times 50 \text{ }\mu\text{m}^2$ spots were studied on each samples too.
28
29
30

31 The transmittance, reflectance and absorptance spectra were measured simultaneously in the
32 300–1400 nm spectral range by photothermal deflection spectroscopy (PDS) setup with 150 W
33 Xe lamp, SpectraPro-150 monochromator (150-mm focal length, $f/4$ -aperture, slits 1/1mm)
34 equipped with two gratings: a UV holographic (1200 /mm) and a ruled (600 /mm) blazed at
35 500 nm, see Figure 1. The spectral resolution was 5 nm with the UV grating and 10 nm with
36 the ruled grating. Samples were immersed during PDS into liquid (Florinert FC72) to measure
37 the relative temperature of the illuminated sample independently for selected photon energies
38 using deflection of probe laser beam. The spectra were spectrally calibrated by measuring PDS
39 of a black carbon sample.
40
41
42
43
44

45 Figure 2 shows the dual beam photocurrent (DBP) setup. The monochromatic light was
46 provided by Xe lamps and Acton Research SpectraPro-275 monochromator equipped with three
47 gratings: 1 (600 gr/mm, blazed at 300 nm), #2 (300 gr/mm, blazed at 750 nm) and #3 (150
48 gr/mm, blazed at 1200 nm). The spectral resolution was 5 nm (10 nm, 20 nm) with the grating
49 #1 (#2, #3). The monochromator covered the spectral range 260 – 1500 nm with the Xe lamp
50 and 500 – 2400 nm with the halogen lamp used as a light source. The intensity of light was
51 modulated by a mechanical chopper (CH) placed just behind the filter wheel (FW). FW contains
52 the following band pass and long pass filters: eSource Optics 25270FBB (260–280 nm),
53 Thorlabs FGUV11-UV (280–380 nm), Thorlabs FGB39 (380-560 nm), Thorlabs FGL550S &
54 FGS550 (560–750 nm), FGL715 (750–1300 nm) and 3 mm thick Si wafer (1300–2400 nm).
55 The light was collimated and focused by 90-degrees off-axis mirrors (focal length 150 mm).
56 The light intensity is monitored via beamsplitter (BS) by Si photodiode used as an auxiliary
57 detector (D) connected to the lock-in-amplifier (L1) referenced to the chopper frequency. UV
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 LED 365 nm (5mW) operating in a continuous mode was used as a secondary light source. The
2 constant voltage bias (U) was provided by Keithley 6487 Picoammeter & Voltage Source that
3 was used to monitor the dc current and to provide ac current amplification for a second lock-in
4 amplifier (L2) via analog voltage output proportional to measured current.
5

6 **Results and discussion**

7
8 Two $1 \times 1 \mu\text{m}^2$ AFM spots were studied on each sample, one spot on the gold part and one spot
9 on the glass part of the MicruX substrate. AFM topography images were similar on gold and
10 on glass part. Two $50 \times 50 \mu\text{m}^2$ spots were studied on each samples too. The morphologies of
11 three ZnO films are presented in Figure 3 a-c. Growth of a thicker ZnO film (sample C) led to
12 formation of larger ZnO crystals. In these experiments Al doping of ZnO film affect the grain
13 size only slightly. Comparison between ZnO films grown on glass and on gold parts of MicruX
14 substrates and analysis of $50 \times 50 \mu\text{m}^2$ images did not reveal any changes neither in
15 morphology nor in thickness of ZnO films. Figure 3d shows the homogeneous coverage of
16 MicruX substrate with ZnO film (sample C). Figure 3e shows the CPEM (AFM-in-SEM) image
17 of the gold-glass border of $10 \mu\text{m}$ MicruX substrate, covered with the undoped ZnO film
18 (sample A). 3D morphology corresponds to AFM morphology, while the colors correspond to
19 SE intensity. Brighter colors above gold compared to darker colors above glass are caused by
20 better conductivity of gold compared to (nonconductive) glass.
21
22
23
24

25 As expected, the resistivity of Al-doped layer (sample B) is much lower than the resistivity of
26 undoped layers (samples A and C), see Table 1. However, the dark volt-ampere characteristic
27 of undoped ZnO is not ohmic at low voltages, but follows the Mott-Gurney law [21], see Figure
28 4. In the low-voltage regime, the injected carriers control space charge and the electric-field
29 profile is dominated by the drift component of the injected carriers. This results in feedback
30 where the electric field drives the current, which in turn sets up the field. This regime is called
31 the space-charge-limited current [22]. The space-charge effect is common in nominally
32 undoped or lightly doped semiconductors, and it can occur outside the depletion region. Under
33 UV illumination, the undoped ZnO was about three orders more conductive. Thus, undoped
34 ZnO was photosensitive, but the photo-response was slow due to a high concentration of
35 electron traps, see Figure 5. In materials exhibiting persistent conductivity, charge carriers are
36 thermally released from traps long after the light source is removed [16,23]. The persistence
37 of photocurrent in ZnO is related to oxygen vacancies [24]. According to the theory,
38 photoexcitation forms a doubly ionized oxygen vacancy from the neutral oxygen vacancy. The
39 deionization of this vacancy involves a large lattice relaxation which accounts for the
40 photocurrent. It should be noted that the photocurrent decay to original (dark) current value
41 took significantly longer (several hours) then the saturation of the photocurrent that occurred
42 within 1 hour.
43
44
45
46
47

48 Since the high dark current prevents photoconductivity measurements, only the photocurrent
49 spectra of the undoped samples were measurable. Figure 6 shows the transmittance (T),
50 reflectance (R) and absorptance (A) spectra of the undoped ZnO layer (sample C) as well as its
51 photocurrent spectra. Absorptance spectrum was measured using PDS and put into the absolute
52 scale using $1-R-T$ spectrum. PC spectra were normalized on A spectra at 3.1 eV. Reflectance
53 interferometry was used to evaluate thin film thickness from interferences in reflectance spectra
54 [13,25,26], see Table 1. The PC spectrum decreases above the optical absorption edge at about
55 3.3 eV because UV light is absorbed at the surface and therefore does not penetrate to IDE.
56 Thus, the photoexcited carriers at the sample surface cannot contribute to the photocurrent. The
57 photocurrent is also lower than the optical absorption below 3 eV. This indicates that the states
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 below the optical absorption edge are defect-related localized states that do not contribute to
2 the electrical conductivity. The mobility edge in semiconductors is defined as the energy level
3 that separates localized states from extended (or delocalized) states in a disordered system [27].
4 Electrons are trapped in localized states—they cannot move freely through the material. These
5 are typically found in the band tails caused by disorder and defects. We can conclude that the
6 mobility edge is about 0.3 eV below the band gap of polycrystalline ZnO prepared by PLD.
7

8 **Conclusion**

9
10 Commercial metal-based IDE are two individually addressable strips of microelectrode arrays
11 on a glass substrate designed for impedance, capacitance, and conductivity measurements. In
12 this paper IDE substrates were used for photoconductivity testing of nanocrystalline ZnO layers
13 prepared by PLD. The advantages of using commercial IDE include easy-to-use, time and cost
14 effectiveness. Moreover, since the IDE can be easily covered by PLD, the electrical properties
15 of the layer deposited on IDE can be measured outside clean rooms. In this paper we have
16 shown that growth of a thicker ZnO film led to formation of larger ZnO crystals whereas Al
17 doping of ZnO film affected the grain size only slightly. IDE substrates were used for
18 photoconductivity testing of polycrystalline ZnO layers deposited on IDE by PLD. We have
19 found that the mobility edge was about 0.3 eV below the band gap of polycrystalline ZnO
20 prepared by PLD. Space-charge-limited currents were observed at low voltages. Persistent
21 photoconductivity indicates potential issues with charge transport due to a high concentration
22 of electron traps below the mobility edge.
23
24
25
26

27 **Author contributions**

28 ZR: Resources, Writing—original draft, Writing—review & editing. NN: Writing—review & editing.
29 NJ: Writing—review & editing. RKS: Writing—review & editing. JH: Writing—review & editing. EU:
30 Writing—review & editing. JK: Writing—review & editing. BR: Writing—review & editing. HSH:
31 Writing—review & editing.
32
33
34
35

36 **Funding**

37 The work was supported by the Czech Science Foundation project 24-10607J and by Czech Ministry of
38 Education, Youth and Sports grant no. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617 - “Energy conversion and
39 storage”. This work was supported by the National Science and Technology Council, Taiwan, for
40 financially supporting this research under Contract No. : NSTC 113-2923-M-153 -001 -MY3.
41
42
43

44 **Data availability**

45 The data are available in a public ASEP repository of the Czech Academy of Sciences (<https://doi.org/...>)
46 accessed on 2025.
47

48 **Conflicts of Interest**

49 The authors declare no conflicts of interest. The funders had no role in the design of the study; in the
50 collection, analyses, or interpretation of data; in the writing of the manuscript; or in the decision to
51 publish the results.
52
53

54 **References**

- 55 1. C. F. Klingshirn, editor, *Zinc Oxide: From Fundamental Properties towards Novel*
56 *Applications* (Springer, 2010).
 - 57 2. C. Klingshirn, *ChemPhysChem* **8**, 782 (2007).
- 58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

3. C. Klingshirn, J. Fallert, H. Zhou, J. Sartor, C. Thiele, F. Maier-Flaig, D. Schneider, and H. Kalt, *Phys. Stat. Sol. (b)* **247**, 1424 (2010).
4. A. Janotti and C. G. Van de Walle, *Rep. Prog. Phys.* **72**, 126501 (2009).
5. Ü. Özgür, Ya. I. Alivov, C. Liu, A. Teke, M. A. Reshchikov, S. Doğan, V. Avrutin, S.-J. Cho, and H. Morkoç, *Journal of Applied Physics* **98**, 041301 (2005).
6. F. Maldonado and A. Stashans, *Journal of Physics and Chemistry of Solids* **71**, 784 (2010).
7. M. Hao, X. Lu, F. Sun, Y. Fu, Y. Ba, Y. Xie, and K. Liu, *Optical Materials* **157**, 116179 (2024).
8. H. Emmanuel Sánchez-Godoy, T. López-Luke, I. Zarazúa, A. Herrera-Rodríguez, J. Castañeda-Contreras, and R. Arturo Rodríguez-Rojas, *Solar Energy* **281**, 112818 (2024).
9. R. Yoo, A. T. Güntner, Y. Park, H. J. Rim, H.-S. Lee, and W. Lee, *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical* **283**, 107 (2019).
10. M. Yang, S. Zhang, F. Qu, S. Gong, C. Wang, L. Qiu, M. Yang, and W. Cheng, *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* **797**, 246 (2019).
11. M. Benamara, P. Rivero-Antúnez, H. Dahman, M. Essid, S. Bouzidi, M. Debliquy, D. Lahem, V. Morales-Flórez, L. Esquivias, J. P. B. Silva, and L. El Mir, *J Sol-Gel Sci Technol* **108**, 13 (2023).
12. A. Sunny and R. Thamankar, *Applied Surface Science* **684**, 161767 (2025).
13. Z. Remes, N. Neykova, N. Jain, R. K. Sharma, J. Holovsky, E. Ukraintsev, J. Micova, and H. S. Hsu, in *NANOCON 2024 Conference Proceedings* (TANGER Ltd., Ostrava, Czech Republic, EU, Orea Congress Hotel Brno, Czech Republic, EU, 2024), pp. 291–296.
14. I. Ayoub, V. Kumar, R. Abolhassani, R. Sehgal, V. Sharma, R. Sehgal, H. C. Swart, and Y. K. Mishra, *Nanotechnology Reviews* **11**, 575 (2022).
15. J. L. Lyons, J. B. Varley, D. Steiauf, A. Janotti, and C. G. Van de Walle, *J. Appl. Phys.* **122**, 035704 (2017).
16. Z. Remeš, Z. Hubička, and P. Hubík, *Nanomaterials* **15**, 590 (2025).
17. P. Klapetek, *Quantitative Data Processing in Scanning Probe Microscopy: SPM Applications for Nanometrology*, Second edition (Elsevier, Amsterdam, Netherlands, 2018).
18. D. Nečas and P. Klapetek, *Open Physics* **10**, 181 (2012).
19. D. Rutherford, K. Kolářová, J. Čech, P. Haušild, J. Kuliček, E. Ukraintsev, Š. Stehlík, R. Dao, J. Neuman, and B. Rezek, *Ultramicroscopy* **258**, 113909 (2024).
20. A. Sosna-Głębska, B. Rezek, E. Ukraintsev, and M. Sibiński, *Journal of Luminescence* **272**, 120618 (2024).
21. N. F. Mott and R. W. Gurney, *Electronic Processes in Ionic Crystals*, 1st ed. (Oxford University Press., 1940).
22. S. M. Sze and K. K. Ng, *Physics of Semiconductor Devices*, 3rd ed (Wiley-Interscience, Hoboken, N.J, 2007).
23. S.-L. Gao, L.-P. Qiu, J. Zhang, W.-P. Han, S. Ramakrishna, and Y.-Z. Long, *ACS Appl. Electron. Mater.* **6**, 1542 (2024).
24. Q. Zhu, C. Xie, H. Li, and D. Zeng, *Nano Res.* **9**, 2972 (2016).
25. H. G. Tompkins, *Spectroscopic Ellipsometry and Reflectometry: A User's Guide* (Wiley, New York, 1999).
26. J. I. Pankove, *Optical Processes in Semiconductors*, Unabridged republication, with slight corr (Dover, Mineola [NY], 1975).
27. N. Mott, *J. Phys. C: Solid State Phys.* **20**, 3075 (1987).

Figures

Figure 1

Photothermal deflection (PDS) setup: Xe lamp (Xe), monochromator (MCH), filter wheel (FW), mechanical chopper (CH), 90° off-axis focusing mirror (M1), spherical focusing mirror (M2), beamsplitter (BS), detectors (D1–D3), lock-in amplifiers (L1– L4), HeNe laser (LASER), position detector (P), sample (S)

Figure 2

Dual beam photocurrent (DBP) setup: light source (LS), monochromator (MCH), filter wheel (FW), 90° off-axis focusing mirrors (M1, M2), mechanical chopper (CH), beamsplitter (BS), long pass filter (LP), LED, lock-in amplifiers (L1, L2), current amplifier (CA), picoammeter & voltage source (K6487).

Figure 3. a) AFM topography map of the thinner undoped ZnO film (sample A); Zscale=50 nm; b) AFM topography map of the thicker undoped ZnO film (sample C); Zscale=100 nm; c) AFM topography map of the Al-doped ZnO film (sample B); Zscale=50 nm; d) AFM topography map of a 500 nm thick undoped ZnO film. Zscale=400 nm; e) CPEM image of a 100 nm thick undoped ZnO film.

Figure 4 Volt-ampere characteristics of the undoped ZnO film (sample A) measured in dark and under UV illumination (LED364, 5mW).

Figure 5 Time decay of photocurrent (sample A) measured at voltage 1 V after UV light was switched on/off at 20 s.

Figure 6

The transmittance (T), reflectance (R), absorptance (A) and photocurrent (PC) spectra of the undoped ZnO layer (sample C). PC spectra were normalized on A spectra at 3.1 eV.

Figure 1

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Figure 2

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Figure 3

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Figure 4

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Figure 5

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Figure 6

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65